

FARMERS' SCHEDULING PATTERNS IN ON-DEMAND PRESSURIZED IRRIGATION

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ABSTRACT

Irrigation scheduling results from the irrigator's integration of meteorological, environmental and crop information. In this paper, the irrigation scheduling patterns of a group of irrigators in the Candasnos Water Users Association (WUA), located in north-eastern Spain, were analysed. Scheduling sprinkler and drip irrigation in this WUA shows additional complications due to the sharing of a collective pressurized irrigation network and to the need to file water orders two days in advance of its foreseen use. The database created by a Remote Surveillance and Control System was mined to obtain the time evolution of hydrant operation time during the 2004-2008 irrigation seasons. Records were selected for clearly identified crops and irrigation systems, and for verified water allocations. Hydrant operation showed a relationship with meteorology (precipitation, wind speed, relative humidity and air temperature), although this relationship was often not evident when hydrants were individually analysed. Statistical analyses were run to classify irrigator's scheduling practices, leading to the establishment of ten different groups. The adopted classification criteria included the average number of weekly irrigations, the SD of the number of weekly irrigations and the modal range of the irrigation starting time. The irrigation pattern was determined by the irrigator (56 %), the irrigation system (33 %), and the crop (11 %). Only in a fraction the cases (22 %) the time change in the scheduling pattern responded to a clear time trend; in 39 % of the cases, changes in time appeared random. Further, 45 % of the irrigators used the same irrigation pattern in at least half of their hydrant-years, independently of the crop.

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24 Only 14 % of the irrigators applied different irrigation scheduling patterns to different crops. Our
25 results suggest that irrigators do not find value or do not have the capacity to develop irrigation
26 patterns more consistent and adapted to the local environment, the crops and the irrigation
27 systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

29 On-farm irrigation scheduling is an important topic of study at two different levels. At the farm
30 level, irrigation scheduling will determine crop yield in both quantity and quality. At the collective
31 level, the addition of the irrigation flows demanded at the hydrants of an irrigation network
32 (resulting from farmer's irrigation scheduling), will determine the network demand and operating
33 conditions throughout the irrigation season.

34 Designing an on-farm irrigation schedule in a pressurized irrigation system implies selecting the
35 timing, duration and frequency of the irrigation events (Clemmens, 1987). The search for
36 maximum uniformity and efficiency in each irrigation event is an additional constrain to irrigation
37 scheduling. On-farm irrigation system design determines maximum irrigation uniformity and
38 application efficiency. Reaching maximum performance in each irrigation event will depend on
39 the adequate selection of irrigation time and duration. These variables are selected at the
40 beginning of the irrigation event, although irrigation duration can be modified at any time. In the
41 case of sprinkler irrigation, the environmental conditions (subjected to relevant inter- and intra-
42 day variability) will strongly determine irrigation uniformity and wind drift and evaporation
43 losses. Selecting the most adequate irrigation time and duration will minimize the negative effect
44 of environmental conditions on the performance of each irrigation event (Playán et al., 2005) and
45 will maximize irrigation efficiency and/or crop yield. In pressurised irrigation systems requiring
46 electrical energy input, irrigation timing may result in different costs. For instance, in the current
47 conditions in Spain, energy costs can be tripled during a 24 h period.

48 Collective pressurized irrigation networks are designed to meet certain simultaneity,
49 characterized by the number of open hydrants in each network segment (Lamaddalena and
50 Sagardoy, 2000). During network operation, the time evolution of the number of open hydrants is
51 determined by the physical design of the on-farm irrigation systems, crop water requirements,
52 energy costs and the Water Users Association (WUA) organizational rules. However, the
53 approach of individual farmers to on-farm irrigation scheduling strongly determines hydrant
54 operation, and can provide valuable information for the optimization of irrigation network design
55 and maintenance.

56 In collective pressurized irrigation networks, design decisions often pose relevant constraints to
57 farmer irrigation scheduling. Relevant limitations derive from the installation of flow limiting

58 valves at the hydrants. Flow limits determine the maximum number of sprinklers or drippers in
59 simultaneous operation or the pivot size. Flow limits also determine the maximum crop water
60 requirements that can be met by the irrigation system. This may result in continuous irrigation
61 operation during the period of peak crop water requirements, regardless of the intraday and
62 interday changes in environmental conditions or energy costs. Regarding the WUAs
63 organizational rules, rigid schedules deriving from the planning of pumping stations or energy use
64 can result in severe limitations to farmers' capacity to respond to crop water requirements.

65 On-farm irrigation controllers have been designed to implement farmers' scheduling decisions.
66 However, on-farm controllers have often been reported to complicate the implementation of
67 optimum, environment-sensitive irrigation scheduling (Zapata et al., 2009). Users should master
68 their advanced irrigation controllers in order to implement all features leading to scheduling
69 flexibility. Most of the agricultural irrigation controllers in the market have very limited
70 possibilities in this respect, and have been designed to produce rigid irrigation schedules.

71 If the characteristics of the collective pressurized irrigation network, the on-farm irrigation
72 system and the controller are important for an adequate irrigation schedule, the human factor
73 stands as the most decisive factor. It is the farmer who judges the available information and
74 produces the schedule leading to the execution of an irrigation event. The farmer may also
75 decide to interrupt irrigation when agrometeorological conditions are not suitable for the
76 irrigation system. In order to make these decisions, a farmer can count on several information
77 sources. Web pages have been created to publish current irrigation requirements for the most
78 common crops in a given region (Department of Water Resources, 2011; Government of Aragón,
79 2011). Additionally, continuous education programs are available to farmers, particularly to those
80 established in large irrigation projects. As a consequence, most professional farmers are aware of
81 the effect of agrometeorological conditions on irrigation scheduling (regarding crop water
82 requirements and the effect on sprinkler irrigation performance). This is particularly important in
83 areas characterized by strong winds, since wind speed is the agrometeorological factor most
84 limiting to sprinkler irrigation performance (Tarjuelo et al., 1999; Zapata et al., 2007; Sánchez et
85 al., 2010). In drip irrigation, farmers' scheduling decisions are not so directly influenced by the
86 environment, and often respond to fertigation requirements or to regulated deficit irrigation
87 strategies (Zapata et al., 201Xa and 201Xb).

88 Researchers have paid attention to the effect of farmers' decision making on several aspects of
89 agricultural production. The most common target of these research works is the influence of
90 human factors on decision making about cropping patterns. Research works have focused on
91 issues such as water scarcity (Faysse, 2003), wastewater irrigation (Styczen et al., 2010), or
92 fluctuations in the price of agricultural commodities (Cortignani and Severini, 2009). The effect of
93 the human factor on irrigation decision making has received limited attention in the literature.
94 Clemmens and Dedrick (1992) analyzed a list of candidate factors (including human factors)
95 affecting farm water use in the surface-irrigated area of Maricopa (Arizona, USA). Dechmi et al.
96 (2003) used the same methodology to assess the effect of farmer related variables on seasonal
97 irrigation depth and crop yield. Merot et al. (2008) studied the relationship between irrigation
98 practices and crop management in a surface-irrigated area specializing in hay production. Finally,
99 Brown et al. (2010) developed tools to predict the influence of farmers' irrigation decisions on
100 the final crop yield.

101 The analysis of detailed on-farm pressurized irrigation schedules has not been the target of
102 recent research efforts. Scientific works have often been oriented to simulating and/or
103 recommending irrigation schedules (Cancela et al., 2006; Liyuan et al., 2010). Other studies have
104 focused on monitoring on-farm irrigation, proposing optimum irrigation calendars (Chopart et al.,
105 2007). However, detailed studies of farmer irrigation scheduling can be used to elucidate current
106 trends in on-farm pressurized irrigation. Researchers can use such studies as a source for insight
107 and to validate irrigation decision making models. On the other hand, irrigation engineers can use
108 these analyses as to improve network and on-farm designs. As a consequence, assessing the
109 factors guiding farmers' irrigation scheduling will lead to more water- and cost-effective future
110 pressurized collective irrigation networks.

111 Remote surveillance and control systems (RSCS) are being installed in many irrigation networks in
112 Spain built in this century. These systems can provide valuable information on individual farmers'
113 irrigation schedules. As a consequence, RSCS can not only provide a service to the farmers, but
114 also provide feedback to irrigation practitioners and analysts. This process is often limited by the
115 database structure (not oriented to data analysis) and by the enormous amount of information
116 often produced by these systems. These findings underline the fact that RSCS are rarely designed
117 taking into consideration the long-term feedback value of the information they store. As a
118 consequence, data mining techniques are required to produce useful information for the analysis

119 of farmers' irrigation scheduling. Data mining concerns the extraction of useful information from
120 large amounts of data (Han and Kamber, 2006). In order to obtain knowledge from large
121 databases the first step is data cleaning, followed by data integration if different sources of
122 information are used. Once all information sources are located in the same platform, data
123 selection and transformation will be required if only part of these data is useful or if data
124 presentation is not adequate. Data mining will be followed by pattern evaluation and knowledge
125 presentation.

126 In this work, the RSCS of an on-demand pressurized WUA located in northeastern Spain was
127 analyzed. The research objectives were to: 1) Build a database on hydrant irrigation (30 min
128 interval) for sprinkler and drip irrigation combining crop, year, hydrant, farmer, agrometeorology
129 and irrigation system; 2) Classify the irrigation seasons recorded at the WUA hydrants according
130 to their irrigation scheduling patterns; and 3) Identify and classify patterns in farmers' behavior
131 regarding relevant factors in irrigation decision making.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Area description

The data analysed in this study were obtained at the Candasnos Water Users Association (WUA). The WUA makes part of the *Riegos del Alto Aragón* Project (Lecina et al., 2010). This irrigated area is located in North-eastern Spain, and can irrigate 6,937 ha. Irrigation systems have only been installed in 4,916 ha. The area presents a semi-arid climate, with very hot summers and long, cold winters. The local meteorological characterization in the years of study (2004-2008) was based on the data obtained at the agrometeorological station of Candasnos, belonging to the SIAR network (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, 2011). A summary of the agrometeorological characterization is presented in Table 1. Annual daily temperature (T) fluctuated between -3.9 and 27.7 °C, with an average of 13.8 °C. Annual average reference evapotranspiration (ET₀) and precipitation (P) in this period were 1,232 mm and 324 mm, respectively. The average wind speed (WS) was 2.3 m s⁻¹, a value that often separates adequate and low solid-set sprinkler irrigation performance (Playán and Mateos, 2006).

Among the study years, 2005 was characterized by severe drought induced by low storage at the main *Riegos del Alto Aragón* reservoirs. As a consequence, farmers' irrigation water use was limited to 4,500 m³ ha⁻¹. In fact, 2005 showed the lowest storage at the beginning of the irrigation season, 51% of full capacity. This value should be compared with the average of the study years (77%), and maximum storage in the series (96% in 2007). Regarding storage in August, 2005 was characterized by 29%, while the average for the study years was 49%.

Differences in water application along the study years could also be observed for major crops. In corn, the average crop water requirements (CWR) during the study period was 519 mm, while the average water use was 665 mm. In the case of alfalfa, CWR and water use averaged 635 and 744 mm, respectively. In 2005, water use in both corn and alfalfa were lower than CWR, with average differences of 8 mm for corn and 215 mm for alfalfa. Farmers made an effort to avoid water stress in corn, since this crop is more sensitive to water stress than alfalfa.

WUA irrigation water is stored at a local reservoir located at the head of the pressurized collective network. The difference in elevation between the reservoir and the WUA hydrants provides the network with natural pressure. Furthermore, the reservoir is gravity fed by the Monegros supply channel. As a consequence, the WUA faces irrelevant energy costs. Flow

162 limiting valves were installed in all WUA hydrants, with discharge limits ranging from 8 to 80 L s⁻¹.
163 The most common discharge limits are 8, 10 and 12 L s⁻¹. These discharges derive from a hydrant
164 design criterion of 1.2 - 1.3 L s⁻¹ ha⁻¹. There are exceptions to this rule, represented by maximum
165 values of 4.1 L s⁻¹ ha⁻¹ (additional discharge for small plots) and occasional minimum values of 0.5
166 L s⁻¹ ha⁻¹.

167 A cable-based remote surveillance and control system (RSCS) was installed at the Candasnos
168 WUA in 1998. The system was set to record hydrant discharge every ten minutes (approximately).
169 The RSCS software and computers were upgraded just before this research was performed. This
170 fact made the exploration of the four old hard drives easy: they could be taken to the laboratory
171 for complete analysis. This RSCS contains the oldest data of this nature in the Ebro basin, and
172 therefore represents a very interesting opportunity for the analysis of irrigation patterns.
173 Unfortunately, the RSCS system does not record irrigation management variables. This problem
174 was solved in 2004, when Candasnos started making full use of the Ador software for the
175 management of WUAs (Playán et al., 2007). As a consequence, the data series concerning plots,
176 hydrants, irrigation systems, water users, water uses (crops) and time evolution of hydrant
177 discharge is available from 2004 to 2008. This period corresponds to the time frame of this study.

178 The WUA showed an average of 276 landowners and 131 irrigators in the years of study. The
179 difference between the number of landowners and irrigators derives from the need to cultivate
180 large extensions of irrigated land (irrigators lease landowners' farms) in order to obtain adequate
181 economic return. The average area was 17.43 ha for landowners and 36.85 ha for irrigators.
182 Some of the irrigators do part-time farming in the area.

183 The irrigation system information was individually collated by observing WUA orthophotographs
184 (Ministerio de Medio Ambiente y Medio Rural y Marino, 2011). The most common irrigation
185 system in Candasnos is solid-set, present in 53 % of the WUA area, followed by pivot (40 %) and
186 drip irrigation (7 %). In some plots, pivot(s) and solid-sets are found in combination. In these
187 cases the central part of the plot is pivot irrigated, while the corners are irrigated by solid-sets.
188 The spatial distribution of Irrigation systems was also available from the Ador database.

189 Crop distribution in the WUA changed each year of study (from 2004 to 2008). Summer field
190 crops prevail in the study area: Averaging the study years, alfalfa and corn occupy 20 % and 40 %
191 of the WUA area, respectively. Other relevant crops in the area are the sequence barley/corn and
192 drip irrigated peach, with respective percentage areas of 15 and 7 %.

193 Water management in the study area is based on previous water orders. The WUA is located at
194 the downstream end of a 223 km canal system (Lecina et al., 2010). As a consequence, water
195 used in Candasnos needs to be ordered to the Project office two days in advance. This time is an
196 approximation of the travel time from the main project reservoirs to the local WUA reservoir.
197 Farmers file individual water orders at the WUA office. Confirmation of these orders by WUA
198 officers ensures the supply of the agreed volume of water, except in the case of accidents in the
199 supply network. Orders are stored in the Ador database. Every day, the water orders filed for the
200 day after tomorrow are summarized and sent to the project office *via* Internet. Water orders
201 permit to document water use in parallel of the RSCS system, providing a means for the
202 validation of water use information. However, the need for previous water orders reduces
203 farmers' freedom to use irrigation water: once water is ordered farmers must use it, since the
204 capacity of the WUA reservoir (218,000 m³) only represents 4.4 mm when distributed to the
205 whole irrigated area.

206 **2.2 Data mining: Extraction of knowledge**

207 An exploratory data analysis was performed on the contents of the RSCS hard drives. The tabular
208 information contained in the system only detailed daily water deliveries per hydrant. However, a
209 graphic utility presented daily evolution of discharge per hydrant. As a consequence, a binary
210 search was started in the RSCS system files in order to locate time-discharge records per hydrant.
211 The original records were found in binary Flow Files (FF) and decrypted. Discharge registers were
212 recorded with time intervals ranging between 11 and 18 min. Decryption did not permit to assess
213 the hydrant code in the system used for tabular reports (corresponding to the project hydrant
214 code).

215 The association between decrypted information and hydrant codes was obtained by comparison
216 of the tabulated and computed daily water delivery per hydrant. The first step was to integrate
217 the FF discharge values into daily delivery volume and standardized semi hourly values (FFst). A
218 specific software application compared the water application patterns and performed the
219 association. Manual supervision was used to provide additional certainty. A total of 256 hydrants
220 were associated to FFst discharge files, creating HFFst files. Additionally, the annual water
221 delivery derived from HFFst files was compared to annual water billed to the irrigators through
222 the Ador software. In cases where differences between the two data sources exceeded 8 %, a

223 case by case analysis was performed to detect anomalies, which were often located at the HFFst
224 files (periods without RSCS data).

225 In a further step, a file was produced for each hydrant summarizing the yearly irrigation events.
226 For each identified event, the date and time of irrigation start and end were recorded, as well as
227 the percent daytime and nighttime irrigation, the average discharge and the irrigation volume.
228 Daytime irrigation was assigned between 8.00 and 20:00 (local civil time). This file contained
229 information about 75,546 irrigation events corresponding to 1,216 hydrant-year combinations.

230 **2.3 Data mining. Selection of valid information**

231 A relational database was created containing all data sources used for this research: HFFst,
232 irrigation events, daily delivery volume per hydrant, agrometeorological data and a number of
233 tables copied from the Ador database: crops, irrigation network, hydrants, irrigation system,
234 landowners, irrigators and plot areas.

235 A series of queries to the relational database were used to obtain specialized information. In a
236 first step, graphics of daily delivery volume were produced for the available combinations of crop,
237 hydrant and year. Individual visual inspection of these graphs was used to discard cases of
238 hydrant-year combinations revealing failed crops or clear errors in crop declaration by farmers. In
239 a second step, a table was created containing hydrant name, cadastral identification, plot area
240 and irrigation system. Since two sources of information were available for plot irrigation systems,
241 plots showing discrepancies were discarded from the database. Finally, hydrants shared among
242 various plots were eliminated because it was not possible to distinguish from the RSCS the plot
243 receiving a given irrigation event. As a consequence of this process, a final database was
244 established containing 39,909 irrigation events resulting from 585 hydrant-year combinations.

245 **2.4 Statistical analyses**

246 The file containing irrigation events was used to elaborate basic statistics about frequencies and
247 general trends of the irrigators' behaviour. The number of hydrants simultaneously irrigating in
248 each semi-hourly period was used for comparison with agrometeorological data. This permitted
249 to analyse the influence of meteorology on sprinkler irrigation decision making. The
250 meteorological factors used in this study included wind velocity, daily precipitation, temperature
251 and relative humidity.

252 The irrigation events file was used for more involved analyses. In a first step, a hierarchical cluster
253 analysis was used on the three variables: weekly number of irrigation events, standard deviation
254 of weekly irrigation events and statistical mode of the starting hour of the irrigation events. This
255 classification was performed to identify homogeneous groups of irrigation decision making in the
256 WUA. Three additional variables were discarded from the analysis at an early stage: the weekly
257 average irrigation duration, the standard deviation of weekly average irrigation duration, and the
258 percentage of irrigations in which irrigation started during the modal range.

259 Differences among these homogeneous groups were analysed using ANOVA and Duncan tests. In
260 a second step, the influence of the year, crop, irrigator, plot area, hydrant characteristics and
261 irrigation system on irrigation decision making was assessed analysing frequencies and using
262 categorical regression. These analyses were performed using the SPSS v.19 statistical software
263 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 19 for Windows, SPSS Inc, Chicago, USA).
264 Finally, semi hourly hydrant discharge data were transformed into binary semi hourly files with
265 the objective of plotting the identified irrigation patterns.

266

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

267 **3.1 Exploratory statistics: irrigators, plot size and operation time**

268 The data selection process focused on selecting combinations of year-hydrant presenting high
269 data quality. As a consequence, both the number of hydrants and the area under study differed
270 from year to year. The study areas were 2,736, 2,083, 1,919, 2,788 and 861 ha for 2004, 2005,
271 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively (Table 2). The irrigation systems installed in the analysed plots
272 included solid-set, drip, pivot and combinations of pivot and solid-set. Considering the area
273 irrigated in each of the study years, the average of area occupied by solid-set was 54 %.
274 Combinations of pivot and solid-set occupied an average 34 % of the area. Pivot irrigation
275 occupied an average 4 % of the area, and the remaining 8 % was occupied by drip irrigation.

276 Summer field crops were very important in the WUA. Corn and alfalfa occupied an average of 46
277 and 24 % of the studied area, respectively. A certain association could be observed between
278 crops and irrigation systems. This was particularly true in corn, alfalfa and peach trees. Solid-set
279 was installed in 61 % of the corn plots, while 54 % of the area cropped to alfalfa was irrigated by
280 pivots or combinations of pivots and solid-sets. All the area cultivated to peach trees used drip
281 irrigation.

282 The number of irrigators analysed in each study year averaged 71, ranging from 44 in 2008 to 88
283 in 2004. The average irrigated area (all study years) was 28.1 ha per irrigator, with a maximum of
284 32.8 ha per irrigator in 2007 and a minimum of 19.6 ha per irrigator in 2008. The average
285 duration of the irrigation events was 23 hours. This is the time the hydrant is open in each
286 irrigation event. This time is typically very different from the actual irrigation application time in
287 the field, due to the division of the field area into sequentially-irrigated sets or to the passage
288 time of the pivot. Relevant differences were found in the average irrigation time between
289 irrigation systems: 50 hours for pivots, 36 hours for pivot + solid-set, 23 hours for solid-sets and
290 11 hours for drip systems.

291 The starting time of the irrigation events presented two periods of high frequency, located
292 around 8 and 20 hours (Fig. 1). 24 % of the irrigation events started between 07:00 and 09:00,
293 while 30 % started between 19:00 and 21:00. The least frequent times for irrigation start were in
294 the ranges between 13:00 and 15:00 and between 02:00 and 05:00. These periods represent
295 central hours of the day and night, respectively.

296 Irrigation hours were grouped in three-hour blocks and separated by months (Table 3). In this
297 Table, the two peaks presented in Fig. 1 can be identified. Further, the effect of the season can be
298 observed: during the irrigation season (May to September), the most frequent range of irrigation
299 start time was 18:00 to 21:00. Irrigators are thus aware of the advantages of night-time irrigation.
300 The second frequent range of irrigation start during the irrigation season was 6:00 to 9:00. During
301 the off-season months, the most common starting irrigation time range was 09:00 to 12:00,
302 although a different pattern could be observed in April and November.

303 35,152 out of the 39,909 analysed irrigation events were applied during the irrigation season.
304 This represents 88 % of the total, and a monthly average of 7,030 irrigations. In the rest of
305 months, irrigation was much less frequent, with an average of 680 irrigations per month, and a
306 total of 4,757 irrigations.

307 Regarding the percentage of irrigation hours in daytime and nighttime, all months within the
308 irrigation season exceeded 50 % of nighttime irrigation. The month with the highest percentage
309 of nighttime irrigation hours was July, with 58.3 %. During the months falling outside the
310 irrigation season, the percentage of daytime irrigation hours was about 70 %.

311 Figure 2 presents the number of hydrants simultaneously irrigating during each semi hourly value
312 and for each year of study. Since differences among study years in the number of considered
313 hydrants were high, data were standardized dividing by the yearly average of hydrants
314 simultaneously irrigating. A clear decrease in hydrant operation could be observed at the central
315 hours of the day, reaching minimum values between 16:00 and 17:00. Hydrant operation
316 increased along the evening, typically reaching a peak in the early night hours (21:00 - 2:00).
317 These results differ from previous findings by Khadra and Lamaddalena (2010) in southern Italy,
318 where peak irrigation flows were recorded at the central hours of the day (from 9:00 to 17:00). In
319 that study, crops included olive trees and vegetable crops, generally under drip irrigation.
320 Differences in the irrigation system explain the opposite daily water use patterns in both areas,
321 since drip irrigation performance is largely independent of meteorology.

322 Irrigation water was limited in 2005 due to water shortage at the main system reservoirs.
323 Irrigators were more careful about water application, giving preference to the nighttime hours
324 (Fig. 2). Irrigator behavior in this year resulted in the largest differences between the number of
325 hydrants irrigating in daytime hours and nighttime hours. This pattern cannot be explained by
326 differences in evapotranspiration and precipitation at the WUA during the irrigation season. In

327 fact, 2005 was an intermediate meteorological year in comparison with the rest of analysed
328 irrigation seasons. In 2006, a similar situation was announced at the beginning of the season,
329 although water restrictions were finally not applied. Irrigators' behaviour during these years
330 proved that sufficient information about best irrigation management practices was known by the
331 irrigators. However, this information was only put into practice during critical moments. Drought
332 years also illustrate the complexity of water use in the WUA, where a large number of factors
333 determine water application patterns.

334 Figure 3 presents scatter plots between the plot area and the average yearly hydrant irrigation
335 hours. Data are presented for different irrigation systems. In the case of solid-sets, a weak but
336 significant relationship ($R^2=0.15$) was found. For a given plot size, the variability in irrigation hours
337 is influenced by the variability in crops, hydrant discharge and on-farm design. However, this
338 variability basically reveals differences in individual irrigation management practices. It is
339 interesting to note that the variability is severely reduced with increasing plot size. In the case of
340 pivot and pivot + solid-set, a better relationship was found. This seems to be due to the fact that
341 irrigation management in pivots is easier than in solid-sets. Similarities could be appreciated
342 between both irrigation systems: the regression intercept is about 1,300 hours and the slope is 19
343 in solid-set and 13 in pivot(s) + solid-set. Finally, a significant relationship between plot area and
344 irrigation hours could not be established for drip irrigation. Dechmi et al. (2003), in a study about
345 a WUA in northeast of Spain, reported a significant and negative relationship between the plot
346 area and the applied irrigation water depth. The differences between that study and the present
347 results can be attributed to different water costs and agricultural systems.

348 **3.2 Meteorology and irrigation**

349 In order to assess the influence of meteorology on irrigation scheduling, semi-hourly and daily
350 values were analysed in conjunction with the number of simultaneously operating hydrants at a
351 given time. As an example, Figure 4 presents daily precipitation and daily number of hydrants in
352 operation during 2005 and 2006. A decrease in hydrant operation was detected in both years
353 following medium to large precipitation events (exceeding about 10 mm). Despite the oscillations
354 in hydrant operation introduced by a number of additional factors, the effect of precipitation on
355 irrigation scheduling is clear, although moderate: precipitation only occasionally reduced
356 irrigation operation to less than half.

357 The effect of wind speed, temperature and relative humidity on sprinkler irrigation scheduling
358 was analysed using semi-hourly values and only for hydrants with solid-set or pivot + solid-set.
359 Non-parametric correlations were used, determining Spearman's Rho (r_s). Regarding wind speed,
360 monthly correlation analyses were performed from May to September (25 analyses in total). 84 %
361 of these analyses were significant ($P < 0.01$) and showed a negative correlation coefficient. The
362 average value of significant coefficients was -0.285, ranging between -0.113 and -0.552. When
363 similar analyses were performed for temperature and relative humidity, results were more
364 variable. Significant, negative correlations were found in 60 % of the analysed months for air
365 temperature (average r_s of -0.469). Regarding relative humidity, 84 % of r_s coefficients were
366 significant and positive (average of 0.418). The influence of wind speed, relative humidity and air
367 temperature on sprinkler irrigation has been analysed in a number of research works. In the local
368 conditions, Playán et al. (2005) reported a clear relationship between these variables and wind
369 drift and evaporation water losses. Ortiz et al. (2009) experimenting in a different area of
370 semiarid Spain, reported similar results, emphasizing the influence of wind speed. Finally,
371 Tarjuelo et al. (1999) reported on the influence of wind speed on sprinkler irrigation uniformity.

372 Similar correlations were performed in drip irrigation. Opposite results were found, with the
373 correlation between operating hydrants and temperature being significant ($P < 0.01$) and positive
374 in 100 % of the combinations of years and months of the irrigation season. Negative and
375 significant correlations were also detected in 100 % of analyses performed for relative humidity.
376 Finally, 92 % of the correlations with wind speed were significant and positive. These results
377 indicate that drip irrigators effectively searched for "windows of opportunity", in which the
378 irrigation network was not saturated. These periods corresponded to the hours of the day
379 showing worst agrometeorological conditions for sprinkler irrigation.

380 A certain trend could be observed in the global data set to schedule irrigation during times when
381 meteorology is adequate for sprinkler irrigation performance. However, in detailed hydrant
382 analyses, this trend could not be identified. The lack of immediate reaction to meteorology is
383 determined by the fact that farmers order their irrigation water two days in advance, and can not
384 cancel their water orders following a sudden change in meteorology.

385 **3.3 Classification of irrigation patterns**

386 Cluster hierarchical analyses resulted in a total of ten groups of irrigation patterns (labelled A to
387 I). Each of them contained a different number of elements (hydrant-years). Groups were

388 differentiated when separated by more than 6 re-scaled units. Identified groups belong to two
389 hierarchical families. The first one includes groups A to D, while the second includes groups E to I.
390 The distance between both families is 25 re-scaled units. Distances within groups in a given family
391 are variable, ranging between the 5 units separating groups E and F, and the 18 points separating
392 group I from the rest of the second family. Figure 5 presents a scheme of the characteristics of
393 each group in terms of irrigation starting time and number of weekly irrigations. Table 4 presents
394 the number of hydrant-year combinations in each cluster group.

395 In the first family, groups A and D shared a range of morning starting irrigation time (6:00 -
396 12:00), the difference between these groups being the average number of irrigations per week
397 (1.9 and 5.2 irrigations/week for groups A and D, respectively). Standard deviation is also higher
398 in group D than in group A. Similar differences were found between groups B and C, starting
399 irrigation events in the 0:00 – 3:00 range and with averages of 2.3 and 5.2 irrigations/week, for
400 groups B and C, respectively.

401 In the second family, group E shows the lowest number of weekly irrigations (on average, 1.4
402 irrigations/week, SD = 0.6 irrigations/week). This is the only group starting in the afternoon-
403 evening (15:00 - 18:00). Groups F, H and I start irrigating a bit later (18:00 - 21:00), but show
404 relevant differences in irrigation frequency. Group F is characterized by 2.6 irrigations/week,
405 while groups H and I reach 4.6 and 7.6 irrigations/week, respectively. Regarding the standard
406 deviations, the resulting values were 1.6, 2.2 and 3.2 irrigations/week for groups F, H and I,
407 respectively. Finally, group G is similar to H in terms of number of weekly irrigations, but shows a
408 larger variability (SD = 3.0 irrigations/week), and starts irrigating from 18:00 to 0.00.

409 Categorical regression was performed to assess the influence of additional variables in the
410 definition of irrigation pattern groups. Significant variables included the irrigator, with an
411 importance of 56.4 %, the irrigation system (32.9 %), and the crop (10.7 %). The adjusted
412 regression coefficient was 0.736. The irrigation year, the plot size and the maximum hydrant
413 discharge per unit plot area were not statistically significant. Cluster hierarchical analyses have
414 been applied before to agricultural irrigation studies (Karami, 2006). However, this author used
415 the technique for a different purpose: identifying the adequacy of a given irrigation system.

416 Table 4 shows the distribution of cluster groups by crop and by irrigation system. Clear
417 associations could be observed between irrigation systems and cluster groups. This is particularly
418 true for pivot(s)+solid-set with group A (54 % of records) and for drip with group D (89 % of

419 records). Groups H and A are common in solid-sets, with a 42 and 23 % of records, respectively.
420 Group F is quite uniformly distributed across most irrigation systems. Some of these associations
421 stem from the characteristics of the irrigation systems. For instance, long irrigation events are
422 required in pivot irrigation. Some associations could also be observed between crops and groups.
423 Group A (long, low-frequency irrigations) represented 56 and 41 % of records in alfalfa and
424 barley, respectively. Group H (frequent irrigations starting at sunset) led the classification in corn,
425 barley/corn and snap/bean. Finally, cluster D (frequent irrigations starting during the morning)
426 capitalized peach trees. Again, group F was populated by different crops.

427 **3.4 Irrigation patterns, irrigators, irrigation systems and crops**

428 Six examples of irrigation patterns are presented in Figure 6 to illustrate the variability in
429 irrigators' behavior. Subfigures a) and b) present the same hydrant (and irrigator) in different
430 crops and years. Despite the fact that the crops (alfalfa and corn) differ in cropping techniques
431 and irrigation management, group A was assigned to both cases. The main difference between
432 them was the duration of the irrigation events, which in corn were uninterrupted along the peak
433 of the irrigation season. In alfalfa, irrigation was interrupted during hay harvest operations.
434 Subfigures c) and d) present similar traits as subfigures a) and b) (same irrigator, same irrigation
435 system, different crops). However, the irrigation patterns were different: B for subfigure c) and H
436 for subfigure d). The irrigator applied different irrigation scheduling patterns to both crops, giving
437 long irrigations to alfalfa and short, frequent irrigations to corn. These differences cannot be
438 explained by differences in crop water requirements, and derive from the individual preferences
439 of the irrigator. Finally, the last pair of subfigures (e and f) corresponds to two different irrigators.
440 The crop (peach trees) and the irrigation system (drip) are the same in both graphs. Irrigation
441 scheduling patterns were classified in groups D and I for graphs e) and f), respectively. Two
442 management strategies are presented for fruit trees, both with frequent irrigations starting
443 during the daytime. Lamacq (1997) presented a similar effort of graphing irrigation scheduling.
444 Her purpose was to validate a simulation model for irrigation scheduling, not to classify irrigation
445 behavioral patterns.

446 Combinations of the same significant variables (irrigator, irrigation system and crop) were
447 selected to study the distribution of irrigation scheduling pattern groups. A total of 132
448 combinations of these three variables were identified. Each combination included between 2 and
449 12 elements. 40 % of the combinations showed the same irrigation pattern group in all elements;

450 18 % of the combinations showed different groups in the elements, but the groups belonged to
451 the same cluster family. Finally, 42 % of the combinations included elements belonging to
452 different groups and families.

453 An analysis was run on the inter-year variability of irrigator's behavior for all the plots with the
454 same irrigation system. Figure 7 – illustrating this analysis – is again divided in six subfigures.
455 Subfigure a) typifies the irrigator who gets all hydrants classified in the same group. This is the
456 case of 34 % of irrigators, although only half of them (17 %) irrigated more than one hydrant-
457 year. Most drip irrigation farmers showed this behavior, since group D is clearly prevalent in this
458 irrigation system. Subfigure (b) typifies an irrigator that generally followed a given irrigation
459 pattern, but showed an atypical pattern in a given year. No trend in the irrigation schedule
460 pattern can be appreciated in this case. This trait could only be observed in 5 % of the analyzed
461 irrigators. Subfigures c), d) and e) show a certain time trend. Subfigures c) and d) belong to the
462 same irrigator, but differ in the irrigation system. A certain pattern is observed in the first years of
463 the study, with evolution along the years. In fact, in 2008 (subfigure c) or 2007 and 2008
464 (subfigures d and e), the group(s) stabilized. 22 % of the analyzed irrigators presented a certain
465 evolution in their irrigation patterns along the irrigation system. Finally, subfigure f) presents the
466 most common type of irrigators' behavior, with 39 % of the analyzed population. Changes in the
467 group of irrigation pattern are common and do not follow appreciable trends.

468 In the last group analysis, the goal was to assess the irrigation pattern groups applied by each
469 farmer to his crops. All hydrant-years for each farmer were analyzed per group and crop (Figure
470 8). Subfigure a) uses different groups for the same crop (four, in this case) along the study years.
471 20 % of the irrigators followed this behavior. Subfigure b) presents a case typifying an opposite
472 behavior: The irrigation pattern used by a certain irrigator is classified in the same group in all
473 occurrences of the same crop. This behavior could be observed in 21 % of the irrigators, but only
474 4 % of the irrigators in this group had more than one occurrence of the same crop. Subfigure c)
475 typifies crop specialization, with each crop being classified in the same group. Only 14 % of the
476 analyzed irrigators belonged to this category. Subfigure d) shows an opposite behavior to c): all
477 crops are classified in the same group. 8 % of the farmers showed this low-profile irrigation
478 pattern. The remaining 37 % of irrigators were typified in the last category, illustrated by
479 subfigures e) and f). In this case, at least 50 % of the hydrant-year-crops are classified in the same
480 group, while the rest populates other irrigation pattern groups. The prevalence of groups D, E and

481 F (45 % in total) underline the relevance of the irrigator in the irrigation pattern, as announced by
482 the categorical regression analysis.

483 The results above can be connected to the findings of Zapata et al. (2009). These authors
484 analysed sprinkler irrigation scheduling in a WUA located next to *Candasnos* and showing similar
485 traits. Those authors focused on irrigation adequacy, and concluded that the farmers' irrigation
486 scheduling practices limited the yield of field crops. They proposed a collective irrigation
487 controller as a means to better adapt irrigation water application to crop water requirements and
488 to the changing environment. The results of this research point at the same direction. In fact, a
489 wide array of different irrigation scheduling patterns has been identified. Farmers use these
490 patterns in a non-specialized way, and show inconsistencies in their application in time and
491 different crops and irrigation systems. Since the RSCS has long been installed in the analysed
492 WUA, the opportunity arises to use it to distribute centrally elaborated irrigation schedules
493 focusing on water conservation and on farmers' economic return. The research reported in this
494 paper has not addressed any of these issues, but has revealed widespread lack of consistency and
495 specialization in the irrigation scheduling patterns.

4. CONCLUSIONS

497 The fact that WUA water orders need to be filed two days in advance of water use makes it
498 difficult to analyze the effect of meteorology on irrigation management. However, the total
499 number of open hydrants was influenced by precipitation and (in sprinkler irrigation) by wind
500 speed ($r_s = 0.285$), relative humidity ($r_s = 0.418$) and air temperature ($r_s = -0.469$). Drip irrigation
501 hydrants took advantage of the periods with worst agrometeorological conditions for sprinkler
502 irrigation. Both irrigation systems showed complementarity in irrigation scheduling. The starting
503 irrigation time presented two periods of high frequency, located around 8:00 and 20:00 hours.
504 The least frequent times for irrigation start were between 02:00 and 05:00 and between 13:00
505 and 15:00, representing central hours of the day and night periods. Irrigation scheduling patterns
506 could be classified in ten groups according to the average number of weekly irrigations, the SD of
507 the number of weekly irrigations and the modal range of the irrigation starting time. The
508 variables explaining these classifications were the irrigator (56.4 %), the irrigation system
509 (32.9 %), and the crop (10.7 %). The human factor, as an integrator of knowledge and experience,
510 stands as the key variable to explain how irrigation events are programmed in an area. In 22 % of
511 the irrigator–irrigation system combinations, changes in irrigation scheduling patterns seemed to
512 respond to a time trend, a structured change in the abovementioned classification variables.
513 However, in 39 % of the cases, changes in time were relevant but appeared to follow a random
514 distribution. Regarding the irrigators' behavior in different crops, 45 % of the irrigators used the
515 same irrigation pattern in at least half of their hydrant-years, independently of the crop. Only
516 14 % of the irrigators showed specialization, applying different irrigation scheduling patterns to
517 different crops. Irrigation decision making in this WUA seems to be limited by shortages in water
518 storage. However, our results suggest that irrigators do not find value or do not have the capacity
519 to develop irrigation patterns more consistent and adapted to the local environment, the crops
520 and the irrigation systems. The complexity in the irrigator behaviour makes it necessary to
521 compile additional data about the response of water users to factors (economic, social and
522 environmental) determining irrigation water use and irrigation performance. These data will
523 contribute to the future development of advanced irrigation controllers and, therefore, to the
524 optimization of water use in on-demand pressurized irrigation networks. Future research should
525 also assess the trade-off between irrigators' behaviour and water productivity. Detail information

526 on water productivity could either explain the observed behavioural traits or justify the need for
527 the adoption of more specialized behavioural rules.

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528

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634 irrigation systems and years are considered in this analysis.

YEAR	2004		2005		2006		2007		2008		Average
	Value	Month	Value								
Average Daily T (°C)	13.6	-	13.5	-	14.6	-	13.7	-	13.5	-	13.8
Maximum Daily T (°C)	27.8	JUL	27.9	JUL	28.1	JUL	27.5	AUG	27.1	AUG	27.7
Minimum Daily T (°C)	-0.6	JAN	-4.3	DEC	-2.9	DEC	-2.1	JAN	-9.6	DEC	-3.9
Average Daily WS (m s ⁻¹)	2.17	-	2.53	-	2.18	-	2.43	-	2.11	-	2.3
Maximum Daily WS (m s ⁻¹)	9.37	JAN	10.68	FEB	8.97	MAR	9.26	JAN	9.60	MAR	9.6
Maximum Daily P (mm)	29.6	APR	49.2	JUN	27	SEP	14.2	APR	41.8	MAY	32.4
Total P (mm)	359.4	-	335.6	-	262.2	-	194.4	-	470.6	-	324.4
Total ET ₀ (mm)	1141	-	1319	-	1292	-	1261	-	1147	-	1232

Table 1. Agrometeorological characterization of the Candasnos Water Users Association in the years of study (2004-2008). Values of Temperature (T), Wind Speed (WS), Precipitation (P) and Reference Evapotranspiration (ET₀) are presented, along with the month of maximum and minimum values.

Irrigation system	Crop	Year				
		2004	2005	2006	2007	2008
Solid set	Alfalfa	368	287	242	211	68
	Barley/Wheat	10	43	200	132	40
	Barley/Corn	140	7	126	214	27
	Corn	819	698	406	744	297
	Snap/Beans	53	39	61	39	52
	Other	59	0	90	99	7
	TOTAL	1449	1074	1124	1439	491
Drip	Peach trees	176	99	98	221	110
	TOTAL	176	99	98	221	110
Pivot	Alfalfa	50	50	0	50	0
	Barley	0	0	0	0	65
	Corn	0	27	65	65	0
	TOTAL	50	77	65	115	65
Pivot(s) + Solid set	Alfalfa	345	342	332	202	53
	Barley	0	27	23	0	0
	Barley/Corn	92	40	83	164	0
	Corn	422	425	193	589	142
	Snap/Bean	179	0	0	58	0
	Other	23	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	1061	834	632	1013	195	

Table 2. Distribution of main crops and irrigation systems in the Candasnos Water Users Association during the study years. Two crops are often grown in rotation in one year.

Start time range	Month											
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
0 - 3	0.7	1.0	2.9	7.3	6.6	8.2	6.8	5.2	4.5	4.4	0.0	7.7
3 - 6	1.5	2.5	1.8	1.7	1.3	2.2	2.6	1.6	1.8	2.2	0.0	0.0
6 - 9	9.0	15.8	20.9	24.4	21.0	19.9	16.5	17.6	20.9	19.2	0.0	10.8
9 - 12	53.0	36.9	32.8	23.6	13.3	12.3	10.8	11.6	17.2	27.2	0.0	49.2
12 - 15	11.2	20.7	13.2	5.8	4.9	4.0	4.0	4.5	3.6	6.4	60.0	18.5
15 - 18	14.2	16.7	16.2	11.6	10.0	8.5	9.2	8.3	7.3	7.1	20.0	9.2
18 - 21	6.0	5.4	10.2	17.2	27.1	29.6	35.9	37.4	33.7	26.3	20.0	4.6
21 - 0	4.5	1.0	2.0	8.4	16.0	15.2	14.2	13.7	10.9	7.3	0.0	0.0

Table 3. Monthly percentage of irrigation events starting at different time ranges. The most frequent monthly time range is presented in bold type.

Nº Elements	163	36	10	57	9	95	7	194	5
GROUP	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
CROP									
Alfalfa	56	9	0	4	4	15	1	10	1
Barley	41	12	0	2	0	27	0	17	0
Barley/Corn	11	2	4	2	0	24	2	54	0
Corn	18	5	3	6	0	17	2	48	1
Peach tree	0	0	0	89	0	0	0	5	5
Snap/Bean	22	6	0	6	0	28	0	39	0
IRRIGATION SYSTEM									
Solid-set	23	7	2	4	2	17	1	42	1
Drip	0	0	0	89	0	0	0	5	5
Pívot	83	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0
Pívot(s) + Solid-set	50	3	0	5	1	22	1	17	0

Table 4. Frequency of the different irrigation scheduling groups in the main crops and in the different irrigation systems. Frequencies over 20 % are presented in bold type.

Total irrigation events

— 2004 - - - 2005 — 2006 - · - 2007 ····· 2008

Solid-set

Pivot(s)+Solid-set

Drip

■ Precipitation — Hydrants operating

a) Group A - Alfalfa - Pivot+Solid-set

b) Group A - Corn - Pivot+Solid-set

c) Group B - Alfalfa - Solid-set

d) Group H - Corn - Solid-set

e) Group D - Peach tree - Drip

f) Group I - Peach tree - Drip

